
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

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Особенности коммуникативных взаимоотношений младших школьников с расстройством аутистического спектра

Аннотация. В статье раскрываются особенности коммуникативных взаимоотношений детей младшего школьного возраста с расстройством аутистического спектра. Обращается внимание на возникновении серьезных трудностей в общении детей с расстройством аутистического спектра, что затрудняет установление контактов со сверстниками, препятствует становлению у детей полноценных коммуникативных связей с окружающими, а также часто приводит к изоляции и к конфликтам в коллективе сверстников. В зависимости от тяжести аутистических проблем и степенью нарушения психического развития выделяются несколько групп детей с РАС. Рассматривается специфика детей с РАС в младшем школьном возрасте, изучаются труды русских и зарубежных ученых по теме исследования. Делается вывод о необходимости проведения комплексной коррекционной работы по совершенствованию коммуникативных взаимоотношений младших дошкольников.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативные взаимоотношения, трудности общения, дети расстройством аутистического спектра, сверстники.

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Features of communicative relationships of primary school children with autism spectrum disorder

Abstract. The article reveals the peculiarities of the communicative relationships of primary school children with autism spectrum disorder. Attention is drawn to the occurrence of serious difficulties in communicating with children with autism spectrum disorder, which makes it difficult to establish contacts with peers, prevents children from forming full-fledged communicative ties with others, and also often leads to isolation and conflicts in the peer group. Depending on the severity of autistic problems and the degree of mental development disorders, several groups of children with ASD are distinguished. The specifics of children with

ASD in primary school age are considered, the works of Russian and foreign scientists on the research topic are studied. The conclusion is made about the need for comprehensive correctional work to improve the communicative relationships of younger preschoolers.

Key words: communicative relationships, communication difficulties, children with autism spectrum disorder, peers.

Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) today is a fairly common problem of younger children, and, to a greater extent, are characterized by a violation of communication functions and social skills. The most common are affective problems and difficulties in the development of active relationships with a constantly changing environment, the attitude to maintaining constancy in the environment and the stereotyping of children's own behavior. ASD is associated with a special systemic disorder of a child's mental development, manifested in the formation of his affective-volitional sphere, in cognitive and personal development [1, p. 301].

The specifics of children with ASD in primary school age are extremely heterogeneous. It is known that the difficulties of most children with mental retardation and other diseases can very often be caused by autism traits. To date, it has been proven that children with autism spectrum disorder are often found among those who successfully master secondary education [2, p. 351].

The results of the study of domestic and foreign scientists confirm the fact that the problems of the autistic spectrum have a biological origin, but their exact causes are of different nature. The presence of ASD makes its mark on the nature and system of disorders of the child's mental development as a whole, is decisive in the appearance of learning difficulties, has an impact on the prognosis of social development and adaptation. However, it should be noted that depending on the origin, the degree of distortion of mental development in autism may vary markedly. A child can be outwardly calm, have stable fears, not use the communicative function of speech, use simple verbal turns, but also have a rich and beautiful speech that is ahead of the age norms of complex phrasal speech. Mental retardation of varying degrees is confirmed in

most children, however, autism spectrum disorders are also found in children whose mental development is normal and high. There are often cases when children with autism are gifted. These may be mathematical abilities, artistic talent, exceptional musical ear, etc. [7, p. 144].

Depending on the severity of autistic problems and the degree of mental development disorder, among the most common cases of childhood autism, four groups of children can be distinguished, differing in holistic systemic characteristics of behavior: the nature of selectivity, the possibilities of arbitrary organization, behavior problems, possible forms of social contacts, methods of autostimulation, the level of psychorechological development. Let's give a characteristic, the most significant for the organization of primary education [14, p. 312]:

The first group. Children have almost no active selectivity in contacts with the environment and people, which is manifested in their field behavior. They practically do not respond to treatment and do not use speech or non-verbal means of communication themselves, their autism outwardly manifests itself as detachment from what is happening.

Children do not seem to see or hear, they may not react clearly even to physical discomfort. Nevertheless, using mainly peripheral vision, without listening, and without paying obvious attention to anything, they can show unexpected understanding of what is happening in their behavior [7, p. 70].

With such pronounced violations of the organization of purposeful action, children with great difficulty master self-service skills, as well as communication skills. They are mutated, although it is known that many of them from time to time can repeat after others the word or phrase that attracted them, and sometimes respond and unexpectedly comment on what is happening. These words,

however, without special help, are poorly fixed for active use, remain an echo of what they have seen or heard. In the apparent absence of active speech of their own, their understanding of the reversed speech remains in question. So, children may show obvious confusion, misunderstanding of simple and directly addressed instructions to them and, at the same time, occasionally demonstrate adequate perception of much more complex speech information not directly directed to them and perceived from the conversations of others. When mastering communication skills with the help of cards with images, words, in some cases written speech using a computer keyboard (such cases have been repeatedly registered), these children can show an understanding of what is happening much more complete than is expected by others. They can also show abilities in solving sensorimotor tasks, in actions with boards with inserts, with boxes of forms, their ingenuity is also manifested in actions with household appliances, telephones, home computers. Even about these deeply autistic children, it cannot be said that they do not distinguish a person from others and do not have a need for communication and attachment to loved ones. They separate their own and others, this can be seen by the changing spatial distance and the possibility of tactile contact, they rejoice when they are circled, tossed. It is with an adult that these children show the maximum selectivity available to them: they can take a hand, lead them to the object they need and put an adult's hand on [10, pp. 127-140].

The second group. Children have only the simplest forms of active contact with people, use stereotypical forms of behavior, including speech, strive for scrupulous preservation of constancy and order in the environment. Their autistic attitudes are more expressed in active negativism [12, p. 112].

In comparison with the first, these children are much more active in the development of relationships with the environment. Unlike the passive child of the first group, which is characterized by a lack of active selectivity, the behavior of these children is not field. They develop habitual forms of life, but they

are strictly limited and the child strives to defend their immutability: here the desire to preserve constancy in the environment, in the usual order of life - selectivity in food, clothing, walking route is expressed as much as possible. These children are suspicious of everything new, can show pronounced sensory discomfort, disgust, fear of surprises, they easily fix fright and, accordingly, can accumulate persistent fears. Uncertainty, an unexpected failure in the order of what is happening, can maladapt a child and provoke a behavioral breakdown, which can manifest itself in active negativism, generalized aggression and self-aggression. In familiar, predictable conditions, they can be calm, satisfied and more open to communication. Within this framework, it is easier for them to master social skills and use them independently in familiar situations. In the developed motor skill, such a child can show skill, even skill: beautiful calligraphic handwriting, skill in drawing ornaments, in children's crafts, etc. are not uncommon. The established skills are strong, but they are too rigidly connected with those life situations in which they were developed and special work is needed to transfer them to new conditions. Speech is characterized by stamps, the child's demands are expressed in words and phrases in the infinitive, in the second or third person, formed on the basis of echolalia (repetition of adult words - "cover", "you want to drink" or suitable quotes from songs, cartoons). Speech develops within the framework of a stereotype and is also tied to a certain situation [10, pp. 127-140].

According to the clinical classification, children of the first and second groups belong to the most typical, classical forms of childhood autism described by L. Kanner.

The third group. Children have developed, but extremely rigid forms of contact with the outside world and people – quite complex, but rigid behavior programs (including speech), poorly adapted to changing circumstances and stereotypical hobbies. This creates extreme difficulties in interacting with people and circumstances, their autism manifests itself as preoccupation with their own

stereotypical interests and inability to build dialogic interaction [3, p 175].

These children strive for achievement, success, and their behavior can be called purposeful. The problem is that in order to act actively, they need a full guarantee of success, experiences of risk, uncertainty disorganize them. If, normally, a child's self-esteem is formed in research activities, in the real experience of successes and failures, then for this child, only stable confirmation of his success is important. He is little capable of research, flexible dialogue with circumstances and accepts only those tasks with which he can obviously cope. The stereotyping of these children is more expressed in the desire to preserve not the constancy of their environment, but the immutability of their own program of action, the need to change the program of action along the way (and this is what the dialogue requires) can provoke an affective breakdown in such a child. Relatives, in connection with the desire of such a child to not insist on his own, often evaluate him as a potential leader. This is an erroneous opinion, because the inability to conduct a dialogue, negotiate, find compromises and build cooperation, not only disrupts the interaction of the child with adults, but also throws him out of the children's collective. With the enormous difficulties of building a dialogue with circumstances, children are capable of a detailed monologue. Their speech is grammatically correct, detailed, with a good stock of words can be evaluated as too correct and adult - "phonographic". With the possibility of complex monologues on abstract intellectual topics, it is difficult for these children to maintain a simple conversation [11, p. 66].

Children of this group in the clinical classification can be defined as children with Asperger's syndrome.

The fourth group. For these children, arbitrary organization is very difficult, but in principle accessible. A delay in psychorecological and social development is characteristic. The difficulties of interacting with people and changing circumstances are manifested in the fact that, while mastering interaction skills and social rules of behavior, children stereo-

typically follow them and get lost with an unprepared demand for their change. In relationships with people, they show a delay in emotional development, social immaturity, and naivety. Despite all the difficulties, their autism is the least profound, it no longer acts as a protective installation, but as the difficulties of communication lying on the surface - vulnerability, inhibition in contacts and problems of organizing dialogue and arbitrary interaction [5, p. 286].

The limitations of such a child are manifested in the fact that he seeks to build his relationship with the world only indirectly, through an adult. With his help, he controls contacts with the environment, and tries to gain stability in an unstable situation. Outside of the mastered and committed rules of behavior, these children organize themselves very poorly, easily get overexcited and become impulsive. It is clear that in these conditions, the child is especially sensitive to a violation of contact, a negative assessment of an adult. Having lost contact with his emotional donor, translator and coordinator of the meanings of what is happening around, such a child stops developing and can regress to the level characteristic of children of the second group. Nevertheless, with all the dependence on another person, among all autistic children, only children of the fourth group try to enter into a dialogue with circumstances (effective and verbal), although they have huge difficulties in organizing it. The mental development of such children goes with a more uniform lag. The awkwardness of large and small motor skills, uncoordinated movements, difficulties in mastering self-service skills are characteristic; the delay in the formation of speech, its indistinctness, weak articulation, poverty of active vocabulary, late appearing, agrammatic phrase; slowness, irregularity in intellectual activity, insufficiency and fragmentation of ideas about the environment, limited play and fantasy. Unlike the children of the third group, the achievements here are more manifested in the nonverbal area, possibly in construction. Children of the fourth group use ready-made stereotypes to a lesser extent - they try to speak and act spontaneously, enter

into a verbal and effective dialogue with the environment. It is in these progressive attempts to communicate, imitate, and learn for their development that they show their awkwardness [8, pp. 408-410].

These children are described in the literature as highly functional children with autism.

In the psychological and pedagogical literature, there are four groups of children suffering from autism spectrum disorders, which are characterized by systemic characteristics of behavior: the nature of selectivity, the possibilities of arbitrary organization, behavior problems, possible forms of social contacts, methods of autostimulation, the level of psychorechological development.

School age is the period of the most pronounced, "classic" manifestations of autism. This is the time of the established pattern of manifestations of races.

The child has already formed ways of autistic protection against interference in his life. By the age of seven, the main features of the manifestation of ASD finally take shape: autism itself as a deep detachment, negativism, absorption in strange hobbies or extreme difficulties in organizing interaction and rigid stereotyping (the desire to defend immutability in the environment, one's own stereotypical actions). Attempts of active intervention by adults in the lives of children, violations of the stereotype of life that has developed in them usually end dramatically: the negativity of the child is fixed, fears increase, the frequency and intensity of aggressive and self-aggressive reactions increase, stereotypical methods of autostimulation that close it from the outside world increase and improve [4].

The contradiction that we managed to fix is interpreted as follows: on the one hand, students with ASD do not find the need to communicate with their peers or this need is distorted, on the other hand, when they get into the microsociety of the class, they become involuntary participants in this collective, which means that there is a need for purposeful work on the formation of skills for

building their communicative interaction with peers.

The most pressing issues that arise not only in theory, but also in practice:

- how to teach children with ASD to pay attention to their peers?
- what ways can children with ASD develop a communication skill with their peers during joint activities?

These and other questions arise before teachers-defectologists and psychologists very often, since there are no similar manifestations in the violation of the behavior of children with autism, which means that each student needs an individual educational route in which the main directions of work and all the methods and techniques that will be used by all participants in the educational process – training and correction to establish contact with peers, teachers and the environment are prescribed.

Having analyzed numerous data on the first months of life of autistic children of various groups, scientists O.S.Nikolskaya, E.R. Baenskaya, M.M. Liebling saw the presence of specific features that distinguish autistic development from normal. Moreover, already at the early stages of the life of an autistic child, there are trends characteristic of the formation of a particular group of early childhood autism [5, p. 286].

The first group. Parents' memories of the first year of life of such children are usually the brightest. From an early age, they amazed others with their attentive, "intelligent" look, an adult, very meaningful facial expression. Such a child was calm, "comfortable", passively obeyed all regime requirements, was plastic and malleable to the manipulations of his mother.

Throughout the first year of life, there was no further development of the initial stage of infection. The child could safely go into the arms of a stranger, he did not have a "fear of a stranger". Such a child never dragged anything into his mouth until a year old, he could be left alone in the crib, knowing that he would not protest. At the same time, it was in these children at a very early age that a special sensitivity (sensitivity) to

sensory stimuli of increased intensity, especially to sounds, was noted [9, pp. 18-24].

The baby could be afraid of the buzzing of a coffee grinder, electric shaver, rattle crackling. At 2-3 years of age, children have paradoxical reactions to strong stimuli, for example, lack of response to cold and pain. A pronounced reaction to a loud sound may also disappear, so much so that the baby's relatives sometimes have suspicions about a decrease in his hearing. Early anxiety of parents occurs closer to two years. Often relatives remember that, standing firmly on his feet, he immediately ran. He does not react to the treatment of adults, does not respond to the name, does not follow the pointing gesture, does not look into the face of his mother. Gradually, his behavior becomes predominantly field.

The second group. Even in infancy, the children of this group have much more problems with caring for them. They are more active, more demanding. This child often dictates to his mother how he should be treated. The constant presence of the mother is necessary for him as a basic condition of existence. With age, this trend does not smooth out, but, on the contrary, sometimes increases. A pronounced tendency to maintain constancy in such a child is found in almost all manifestations of his activity even before the year, and at the age of 2-3 years it already looks like a pathological symptom [8, pp. 408-410].

By this time, a certain set of habitual actions accumulates, which make up every day of the child, and which he does not allow to change: the same walking route, listening to the same record, etc.

The child of this group is especially sensitive to compliance with the regime with all its smallest details. From an early age, the child shows a special sensitivity to the sensory parameters of the surrounding world.

The third group. In children of this group, sensory vulnerability was also quite evident in the first year of life. They often had serious diathesis, a tendency to allergic reactions. In the first months of life, the child could be tearful, restless, difficult to fall asleep. The child of the third group identifies loved ones early and especially the mother, of

course, becomes attached to them. Sometimes there was a paradoxical reaction when the child, apparently, was guided by the intensity of the impact, and not by its qualities (for example, a five-month-old baby could burst into tears when his father laughed). When these children get the opportunity to move independently, they are uncontrollably captured by field behavior, he is attracted by individual impressions, he has special drives early [13, p. 80]. The fourth group. In the most "prosperous" children of the fourth group, the early stages of development are as close as possible to the norm. However, in general, their development looks more delayed than in children of group 3.

First of all, this concerns motor skills and speech; there is also a general decrease in tone, slight inhibition. Children of this group are affectionate, affectionate in emotional contacts with relatives. They are in a very close relationship with their mother. However, before reaching the age of one, they refuse to interfere with their loved ones in their studies; it is difficult to teach him anything, he prefers to reach everything himself [3, p. 175].

The issue of intellectual development of children with early autism syndrome is not resolved. A catamnestic study of a group of children with one of the clinical forms of this syndrome showed that 2/3 of the observations had a pronounced lag in mental development, whereas 1/3 of the patients had intelligence within normal limits, and these children eventually adapted sufficiently socially.

Only in a small percentage of cases, children with a well-established diagnosis of autism can continue to live independently only 1-2 out of 100. 25-30% of patients develop epilepsy. Most remain disabled for life.

So, a theoretical analysis of the literature has shown that communicative abilities are based on motivated interaction with each other, with the team. When educating communicative abilities, it is necessary to take into account the psychological and pedagogical features of younger schoolchildren, since a group of peers becomes a kind of filter for a younger student through which he passes the

values of parents, deciding which ones to discard and which ones to focus on in the future.

Thus, in the psychological and pedagogical literature, four groups of children suffering from autism spectrum disorders are distinguished, which are characterized by sys-

temic characteristics of behavior: the nature of selectivity, the possibilities of arbitrary organization, behavior problems, possible forms of social contacts, methods of autostimulation, the level of psychorechological development.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Autism. Methodological recommendations for correctional work. [Text] /Edited by S.A.Morozov (materials for the special course). Moscow: Signal, 2003.p. 301.
2. Belopolskaya, N.L. Children's pathopsychology. Moscow: Kogito-Tsentr, 2001. p. 351.
3. Children's logopsychology: textbook / edited by V. I. Seliverstov. Moscow: Vlados, 2008. p. 175.
4. Vyunova E.A. Diagnostics and psychological and pedagogical support of children with early childhood autism syndrome // Psychologist in kindergarten. Moscow, 2005. No. 3.
5. Ekzhanova, E. A. Fundamentals of integrated learning / E.A. Ekzhanova, E.V. Reznikova. Moscow: Bustard, 2008. 286 p.
6. Gilbert, K. Autism. Medical and pedagogical impact. M.: Vlados, 2005.
7. Karvasarskaya, I.B. Aside. From experience working with autistic children. Moscow: Enlightenment, 2003.
8. Khaustov, A.V. The problem of social interaction and communication in children with early childhood autism // Modern trends in special pedagogy and psychology. Scientific works of the All-Russian Scientific and Practical Conference. Samara, 2003. pp. 408-410.
9. Khaustov, A.V. The study of communication skills of children with autism in foreign literature // Children with developmental problems. 2005. No. 3. pp. 18-24.
10. Methods of educational work in the center of correctional and developmental training and rehabilitation: studies.-method. manual / M. Ventland, S.E. Gaidukevich, T.V. Gorudko, etc. Minsk: BSPU, 2009. pp. 127-140.
11. Morozova, S.S. Autism: correctional work in severe and complicated forms. M.: Vlados, 2007. p. 66.
12. Nurieva, L.G. Speech development in autistic children. Moscow: Terevinf, 2007. p. 112.
13. Teaching children with autism spectrum disorders. Methodological recommendations for teachers and support specialists of the primary school. Ed. by S.V. Alyokhin // Under the general editorship of N.Ya. Semago. Moscow: MGPPU, 2012. p. 80.
14. Wenger A. L. Special pedagogy: textbook. Mosow: Akademiya, 2002 p. 312.

REFERENCES (TRANSLITERATED)

1. Autism. Methodological recommendations for correctional work. [Text] /Edited by S.A.Morozov (materials for the special course). Moscow: Signal, 2003.p. 301.
2. Belopolskaya, N.L. Children's pathopsychology. Moscow: Kogito-Tsentr, 2001. p. 351.
3. Children's logopsychology: textbook / edited by V. I. Seliverstov. Moscow: Vlados, 2008. p. 175.
4. Vyunova E.A. Diagnostics and psychological and pedagogical support of children with early childhood autism syndrome // Psychologist in kindergarten. Moscow, 2005. No. 3.
5. Ekzhanova, E. A. Fundamentals of integrated learning / E.A. Ekzhanova, E.V. Reznikova. Moscow: Bustard, 2008. 286 p.
6. Gilbert, K. Autism. Medical and pedagogical impact. M.: Vlados, 2005.
7. Karvasarskaya, I.B. Aside. From experience working with autistic children. Moscow: Enlightenment, 2003.
8. Khaustov, A.V. The problem of social interaction and communication in children with early childhood autism // Modern trends in special pedagogy and psychology. Scientific works of the All-Russian Scientific and Practical Conference. Samara, 2003. pp. 408-410.
9. Khaustov, A.V. The study of communication skills of children with autism in foreign literature // Children with developmental problems. 2005. No. 3. pp. 18-24.

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10. Methods of educational work in the center of correctional and developmental training and rehabilitation: studies.-method. manual / M. Ventland, S.E. Gaidukevich, T.V. Gorudko, etc. Minsk: BSPU, 2009. pp. 127-140.
 11. Morozova, S.S. Autism: correctional work in severe and complicated forms. M.: Vlados, 2007. p. 66.
 12. Nurieva, L.G. Speech development in autistic children. Moscow: Terevinf, 2007. p. 112.
 13. Teaching children with autism spectrum disorders. Methodological recommendations for teachers and support specialists of the primary school. Ed. by S.V. Alyokhin // Under the general editorship of N.Ya. Semago. Moscow: MGPPU, 2012. p. 80.
 14. Wenger A. L. Special pedagogy: textbook. Mosow: Akademiya, 2002 p. 312.

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